

BORDER INVIOLENCE AND THE CRISIS OF SECURITY GUARANTEES: Ukraine between agreements of the past and war of the present

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The article analyzes the international legal principles of the territorial integrity of Ukraine and reveals the reasons for the collapse of security guarantees provided to the state in different periods from 1991 to the beginning of the full-scale aggression of the Russian Federation in 2022. Based on the Constitution of Ukraine, bilateral peace and border agreements, the Budapest Memorandum, and resolutions of the UN General Assembly, the phenomenon of *bad peace* is studied, as well as its threat to the modern international system. The author concludes on the legal impossibility of any territorial concessions by Ukraine and justifies why compromises with the aggressor can create the prerequisites for a new war in Europe.

Keywords: inviolability of borders, crisis of security guarantees, concessions, compromises, modern war, power of world diplomacy

Introduction.

The issue of inviolability of state borders and binding international security guarantees has become key in the 21st century, using the example of Ukraine. After gaining independence in 1991, the state received wide international recognition, signed a number of treaties with the Russian Federation, gave up the world's third-largest nuclear arsenal in exchange for security guarantees, and became the subject of dozens of UN General Assembly resolutions supporting its sovereignty. However, the Russian aggression of 2014, the subsequent annexation of Crimea, and the full-scale invasion of 2022 exposed the crisis of international security mechanisms and the legitimacy of peace agreements that were not backed by coercive mechanisms. By researching and analyzing all key documents — from the Constitution of Ukraine to the Budapest Memorandum — it sheds light on why a bad peace will not only fail to stop the aggressor, but will also create the conditions for a potential escalation of a third European war.

1 Constitutional foundations of the inviolability of Ukraine's borders

The Constitution of Ukraine defines the territory of the state as integral and inviolable (Article 2), and any changes to the borders are possible only through an all-Ukrainian referendum (Article 73).

This means that the authorities have no right to negotiate the transfer of territories and no international treaty can contradict the Constitution of Ukraine, because the renunciation of part of the territory is legally impossible within the current state system.

Thus, proposals of any initiatives can in no case put on the table of peace negotiations the issue of exchanging territory for security, because this contradicts the Fundamental Law of Ukraine and has no legal force.

After the declaration of independence, Ukraine received official recognition from the Russian Federation on December 5, 1991. Later, the parties concluded a number of agreements that confirmed the status of the borders:

- Treaty on the Ukrainian - Russian State Border,
- Agreement on its Demarcation,
- The Great Treaty on Friendship, Cooperation and Partnership (1997), which contained a direct obligation of the parties to respect each other's borders.

These documents created a powerful legal framework that Russia violated in 2014 and 2022, effectively abandoning its own international promises. Due to the fact that Europe did not react immediately in 2014 - 2022 happened - it is not known what Europe should expect in 2030. Ukraine, having voluntarily renounced nuclear weapons, received assurances from the guarantor countries USA, Great Britain, Russia regarding: respect for independence and borders, refraining from the threat of force and economic pressure, action through the UN Security Council in the event of aggression. Since the guarantee mechanism was not legally binding and did not contain coercive instruments, democracy is a good and philosophical science to this day. That is why Russian aggression demonstrated the crisis of the model of security guarantees without a defender, the insufficiency of international instruments for the protection of non-nuclear states and the fundamental problem of trust in the nuclear non-proliferation system (NPT). Ukraine has become an example of how voluntary nuclear disarmament may not prevent aggression.

Everyone has witnessed the role the UN has played in resolutions as an instrument for restoring international legal order. The UN General Assembly has adopted a number of resolutions (68/262, ES-11/1-ES-11/8, etc.), which confirmed the territorial integrity of Ukraine, condemned the aggression of the Russian Federation, demanded the withdrawal of troops, defined Russia's actions as a violation of the UN Charter, and the like.

Despite this, UN resolutions have no executive mechanism, and the veto right in the Security Council blocks real sanction actions against the aggressor. This is a common manifestation of the weakness of the modern international security system and raises the issue of its reform as soon as possible. There are enough institutions in the European Union that would be able to correct these shortcomings of the system, but there is no will to direct action.

2. The phenomenon of bad peace and the realities of the 21st century

The European tradition of realpolitik was established on Cold War theories and was often based on temporary compromises with a stronger subject (now the realization has come that Russia is more deceitful than ever). However, in the 21st century, the totalitarian regime uses

compromise as a tool for a new offensive. It interprets concessions to the aggressor as weakness, and the frozen conflict will turn into a preparatory stage for a full-scale war.

The Ukrainian experience of 2014–2021 has clearly proven this. Any *peace* that involves territorial concessions historically does not interrupt the war — it only postpones it. So, isn't it easier for Europe to add some military and diplomatic efforts (I am convinced that Germany would find the leverage of diplomatic power in negotiations with the aggressor, its generously financed friend) and end the wars on the territory of Ukraine, rather than inviting war into Europe. 3. Territorial compromises are legally and strategically impossible for Ukraine. Impossible because there is a constitutional prohibition - borders can only be changed through a referendum. International obligations on recognized borders have already been confirmed by dozens of documents. If the concession of the Russian Federation is legitimized, it will lead to a world policy of forcible seizure of territories. There are many willing ones who are waiting. In other words, such concessions would become a precedent for other aggressors, who are often financed by the Russian Federation to destabilize the world order in various ways. Lack of punishment - generates a repetition of aggression. The risk of a new war can be calculated by mathematical probability theory. Giving up territories will only create additional uncontrolled zones that will become a springboard for a new offensive. National security should not take such risks. Thus, Ukraine's position is not only legally justified, but also strategically necessary for the stability of all of Europe. And a united Europe must find a single wise solution to the Ukrainian issue. This is its vital step towards a bright future that is so clearly planned.

Conclusions

Ukraine has found itself at the center of the greatest security challenge of the 21st century, which has revealed the weaknesses of international security guarantees, the crisis of UN institutions, the ineffectiveness of memorandums without implementation mechanisms, and the danger of the proposed peace that rewards the aggressor.

The inviolability of Ukrainian borders is not a political position or a negotiating line. It is: a requirement of international law, a constitutional obligation, the basis of European Security.

The war of today has shown: only a just peace, not territorial compromises, can ensure stability in the region and long-term security of Ukraine. This is a war of the 21st century, and therefore no experience of other states can be used. There is no need to drag out the war either, but to put pressure on European partners by all effective and existing methods and together with them to seek ways to resolve the situation. The limits of intransigence must be clearly defined. And, after all, Germany has never been subordinate to the Russian Federation in espionage (Germany cares about its own economic prosperity the most, Ukraine should find the way to attract it with mutual benefits in order to get optimal results in peacemaking process).

References

Constitution of Ukraine

Recognition of the russian federation's independence of Ukraine (05.12.1991)

Treaties on the state border and its demarcation

Great Treaty of Friendship (1997)

Budapest Memorandum (1994)

UN General Assembly Resolution 68/262

Resolutions ES-11/1 – ES-11/8

UN Security Council Resolution 2623

Appendix: The main principles of the armistice. Scientific presentation.

No territorial concessions (Constitution of Ukraine vs international law).

International monitoring and implementation of obligations -
without this, the russian federation will violate the agreement.

Transparency and phasing with clear dates and responsibility for disruption.
Sovereignty of Ukraine throughout its territory.

1. Implement this in the same way as the laying of the Nord Stream pipeline

Complete ceasefire

Fixing the date and time of the cessation of hostilities.

Monitoring mechanism - with the participation of the UN or another international mission.

Creation of safe humanitarian corridors.

2. Withdrawal of russian troops

Phase-wise, but with specific deadlines.

Includes regular troops, special forces, private military structures, etc.

Presentation to the russian federation of the full list of units being withdrawn.

3. Restoration of Ukraine's control over the state border

Transfer of control to international observers for a transitional period.

Gradual transfer of powers to Ukrainian border guards.

Technical support from the EU/OSCE/UN (not enough people or funds / announce a gathering of volunteers from Europe - the old diaspora is ready to join)

4. Release of all prisoners and illegally detained persons

All under international control, plus those, for whom is not *convenient* in Ukraine

Release of civilians, deportees, children, incl. korea and china.

5. Security guarantees for Ukraine

International treaty on protection from new aggression.

Clear response mechanisms (sanctions, military aid, protective mechanisms).
Involvement of several guarantor states.

6. International interim administration in the deoccupied territories (if necessary)
UN mandate or coalition of countries (do not provide - raise the issue of dissolving the UN, as once the League of Nations, which could not cope with the requirements)
Restoration of institutions, police, courts.
Protection of the civilian population (cleansing territories from groups of the occupier throughout the country as a threat to development and democracy). Adopt the experience of lustrations.

7. Deoccupation and demilitarization of territories
Removal of explosives, demining.
Restore Ukrainian authorities.
Prohibition of encroaching on a place in power by those who are “obvious” and “famous”.

8. International register of destruction and compensation
Creation of a compensation fund, oligarchs - who wish to stay in the country (can contribute to the restoration of the country, but they must not be seen or heard)
Linking compensation to sanctions and international assets of the Russian Federation.
Transparent procedure for submitting applications.

9. Judicial and legal mechanisms
Investigation of war crimes by non-retroactive international institutions (ICC).
Guarantees of the safety of evidence and witnesses

10. Procedure for restoring normal diplomatic contacts (step by step)
First technical channels. Then consular.
Political contacts - would drag on for a long time.

11. Mechanism of immediate reaction to violation of the ceasefire
Automatic sanctions.
Possibility of rapid convening of the UN Security Council or the Council of Europe.
Ukraine's right to turn to international partners for immediate assistance.

12. Guarantee of inviolability of borders
The ceasefire cannot contain clauses on changing the territory of Ukraine.
No *referendums* under occupation.
Borders are determined by the Constitution of Ukraine and international law.